

Vibration of Yukawa Potential Dependent Time and Extended Klein-Gordon Equation in Rindler Space-Time

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Abstract: Atom's nucleus force understand by Yukawa potential independent time. We study Yukawa potential dependent about time. We make Klein-Gordon equation is satisfied by Yukawa potential dependent about time. Yukawa potential satisfy Proca equation or Klein-Gordon equation. If we represent Yukawa potential dependent time in Rindler space-time, this Yukawa potential satisfy the extended Klein-Gordon equation in Rindler space-time. We understand Yukawa force in Rindler space-time.

Keywords: Nucleus vibration; Yukawa potential; Klein-Gordon equation Rindler Space-time; Extended Klein-Gordon equation Yukawa force

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1. INTRODUCTION

Atom's nucleus force understand by Yukawa potential. We study Yukawa potential dependent about time. We make Klein-Gordon equation is satisfied by Yukawa potential dependent about time.

At first, Yukawa potential V describes nucleus's combine force in semi-classical method.[7]

$$V = -\frac{g^2}{r} \exp\left(-\frac{m_{\pi} r c}{\hbar}\right)$$

g is real number, m_{π} is the meson's mass (1)

Klein-Gordon equation is satisfied by Yukawa potential V .

$$-\partial_{\mu} \partial^{\mu} V + \frac{m_{\pi}^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} V = -\nabla^2 V + \frac{m_{\pi}^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} V = 0$$

$$V = -\frac{g^2}{r} \exp\left(-\frac{m_{\pi} r c}{\hbar}\right) \quad (2)$$

If we focus Klein-Gordon equation make 4-dimentional partial differential equation about Yukawa potential ϕ dependent time,

$$\frac{m_{\pi}^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi + \partial_{\mu} \partial^{\mu} \phi = \frac{m_{\pi}^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \phi - \nabla^2 \phi = 0 \quad (3)$$

In this time, Yukawa potential ϕ dependent time is.

$$\phi = -\frac{g^2}{r} \exp\left(-\frac{m_{\pi} r c}{\hbar}\right) + A_0 \sin \omega t, \quad \text{Frequency } \omega = \frac{m_{\pi} c^2}{\hbar} \quad (4)$$

Absolutely, if we calculate, Eq(3) is satisfied by Eq(4). Yukawa potential ϕ is vibrated about the amplitude A_0 , but we know the nuclear strong force doesn't vibrate about time in inertial frame..

2. YUKAWA POTENTIAL DEPENDENT TIME FROM EXTENDED KLEIN-GORDON EQUATION IN RINDLER-SPACE-TIME

Rindler coordinates are

$$ct = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0}{c} \xi^0\right), \quad x = \left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0}{c} \xi^0\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0}$$

$$y = \xi^2, z = \xi^3 \tag{5}$$

If we write Yukawa potential ϕ in inertial frame,

$$\phi = -\frac{g^2}{r} \exp\left(-\frac{m_\pi r c}{\hbar}\right) + A_0 \sin \omega t, \quad \text{Frequency } \omega = \frac{m_\pi c^2}{\hbar} \tag{6}$$

If we rewrite Yukawa potential ϕ_ξ in Rindler space-time,

$$\phi = \phi^1 + \phi^2 = \phi_\xi = \phi_\xi^1 + \phi_\xi^2 \tag{7}$$

$$\phi^1 = \phi_\xi^1 = -\frac{g^2}{\sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{m_\pi c}{\hbar} \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}\right)$$

$$= -\frac{g^2}{\sqrt{\left\{\left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0}{c} \xi^0\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0}\right\}^2 + (\xi^2)^2 + (\xi^3)^2}} \exp\left[-\frac{m_\pi c}{\hbar} \sqrt{\left\{\left(\frac{c^2}{a_0} + \xi^1\right) \cosh\left(\frac{a_0}{c} \xi^0\right) - \frac{c^2}{a_0}\right\}^2 + (\xi^2)^2 + (\xi^3)^2}\right] \tag{8}$$

And,

$$\phi^2 = \phi_\xi^2 = A_0 \sin \omega t = A_0 \sin \left[\omega \left\{\left(\frac{c}{a_0} + \frac{\xi^1}{c}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}\right)\right\}\right] \tag{9}$$

This Yukawa potential satisfy the extended Klein-Gordon equation. At first, energy and momentum are in Rindler space-time[1],

$$E_\xi = i\hbar \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi^0}, \quad \vec{p}_\xi = -i\hbar \vec{\nabla}_\xi \tag{10}$$

Energy-Momentum equation is in Rindler space-time[1],

$$E_\xi^2 = \vec{p}_\xi \cdot c \cdot \vec{p}_\xi \cdot c + m^2 c^4 \tag{11}$$

Hence, normal Klein-Gordon equation is in Rindler-spacetime,

$$\frac{m_\pi^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi_\xi + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^0{}^2} \phi_\xi - \nabla_\xi^2 \phi_\xi = 0 \tag{12}$$

In this time, we focus the gauge Λ equation in Rindler space-time[1],

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \xi^0{}^2} \Lambda - \nabla_{\xi}^2 \Lambda - \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)} = 0 \quad (13)$$

Hence, Eq(12) change extended Klein-Gordon equation in Rindler space-time.

Extended Klein-Gordon Equation is in Rindler space-time,

$$\frac{m_{\pi}^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi_{\xi}^1 + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_{\xi}^1}{\partial \xi^0{}^2} - \nabla_{\xi}^2 \phi_{\xi}^1 - \frac{\partial \phi_{\xi}^1}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)} = 0 \quad (14)$$

And

$$\frac{m_{\pi}^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi_{\xi}^2 + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_{\xi}^2}{\partial \xi^0{}^2} - \nabla_{\xi}^2 \phi_{\xi}^2 - \frac{\partial \phi_{\xi}^2}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Hence,

$$\frac{m_{\pi}^2 c^2}{\hbar^2} \phi_{\xi} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi_{\xi}}{\partial \xi^0{}^2} - \nabla_{\xi}^2 \phi_{\xi} - \frac{\partial \phi_{\xi}}{\partial \xi^1} \frac{a_0}{c^2} \frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{a_0}{c^2} \xi^1\right)} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Eq(8) ,Eq(9), Yukawa potentials $\phi_{\xi}^1, \phi_{\xi}^2$ satisfy Eq(14),Eq(15), extended Klein-Gordon equations

in Rindler space-time. Therefore, Eq(7), Yukawa potential ϕ_{ξ} satisfy Eq(16), extended Klein-Gordon equation in Rindler space-time

Yukawa force $\vec{f}$ is

$$\vec{f} = -\vec{\nabla} \phi = -\frac{g^2}{r^3} [\exp(-\frac{m_{\pi}rc}{\hbar})] (1 + \frac{m_{\pi}rc}{\hbar}) \vec{r} \quad (17)$$

In this time, Yukawa force $\vec{f}_{\xi}$ is Rindler space-time,

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{f}_{\xi} = -\vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \phi_{\xi} = -\vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \phi_{\xi}^1 - \vec{\nabla}_{\xi} \phi_{\xi}^2 = -\frac{g^2}{r^3} [\exp(-\frac{m_{\pi}rc}{\hbar})] (1 + \frac{m_{\pi}rc}{\hbar}) (x \cosh(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}), \xi^2, \xi^3) \\ - \frac{\omega}{c} A[\cos(\omega t)] (\sinh(\frac{a_0 \xi^0}{c}), 0, 0) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Hence, according to Yukawa force $\vec{f}_{\xi}$ in Rindler space-time, the nuclear force strongly acts and vibrates in accelerated frame rather than inertial frame in x-axis.

3. CONCLUSION

We found Yukawa potential dependent time. Hence, the nuclear strong force vibrates about time in Rindler spacetime. We found Yukawa potential mechanism in Rindler Space-time. We understand nuclear force in Rindler space-time.

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